

BC-SIM-TN-9
STC GM Observation Strategy Optimization
Issue 2.0

Emanuele Simioni¹, Cristina Re¹, Adriano Tullo¹, Michele Zusi²,
Romolo Politi², Vincent Carlier³,
Gabriele Cremonese¹, Fabrizio Capaccioni², Alain Doressundiram³,
Pasquale Palumbo⁵, Mathieu Vincendon⁴,

¹INAF-OAPd, Vicolo Osservatorio 5,35122, Padua, Italy

²INAF-IAPS, Via Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Rome, Italy

³OLESIA (Observatoire de Paris, Laboratoire d'Études Spatiales et d'Instrumentation en Astrophysique), 92195 Meudon Cedex, France

⁴CNRS (Institut d'Astrophysique Spatiale), Université Paris Sud, 91405, Orsay, France

⁵Università Parthenopea, Centro Direzionale Isola 4, 80133, Naples, Italy

Index

APPROVATION.....	3
CHANGE LOG	3
INTRODUCTION	4
SCOPE	4
REFERENCE DOCUMENT	4
ACRONYMS.....	5
DOCUMENT FORMAT AND REPOSITORY	5
DOCUMENT ORGANIZATION.....	6
1. DEFINITIONS AND ASSUMPTIONS	7
1.1. STC CHANNEL	7
1.2. ORBIT AND SK ASSUMPTIONS.....	8
1.2.1. SPICE KERNELS AND SEASONS.....	8
1.2.2. STC GM ORBITS OPERATIVITY	9
2. THE STC GLOBAL MAPPING OPTIMIZATION	10
3. CONSTRAINTS FROM THE INSTRUMENT DESIGN	11
3.1. FIELD OF VIEW AND CHANNELS	11
3.2. STC TYPICAL ORBIT	13
3.2.1. <i>Segments Orbit definition</i>	15
4. PARAMETERS DEFINITION.....	18
4.1. INTEGRATION TIME	18
4.1.1. <i>Assumptions</i>	18
4.1.2. <i>Analysis</i>	18
4.2. AT OVERLAPPING AND REPETITION TIME	19
4.2.1. <i>Assumptions</i>	19
4.2.2. <i>Analysis</i>	20
4.3. CT OVERLAPPING AND CT DIMENSION	22
4.3.1. <i>Assumptions</i>	22
4.3.2. <i>Analysis</i>	22
5. RESULTS	28
5.1. PARAMETERS OVERVIEW.....	28
5.2. DV PRODUCTION	34

Document BC-SIM-TN-009
 Date 18/11/2024
 Issue 1
 Revision 0
 Page 3 of 34

Approval

Edited by:	Emanuele Simioni
	Adriano Tullo
	Cristina Re
	Michele Zusi
Approved by:	Cristina Re
	Gabriele Cremonese

Change Log

Issue	Revision	Date	Affected Pages	Change description
1	0	6/7/2022	All	Draft
2	0	18/11/2024	All	New strategy optimization for STC GM phase. Main changes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Along track and cross track overlapping are updated • The number of orbit sections are updated • STOP TCs are avoided • STC is not in GM mode for more sections of orbits • Aphelion considered are different (due to the change of the mission plan)
2	1	27/11/2024		Table 1 and Figure 12 are corrected and Figure 2 was added.

Document BC-SIM-TN-009
Date 18/11/2024
Issue 1
Revision 0
Page 4 of 34

Introduction

Scope

The present document has been issued to describe the Operation strategy during the Global Mapping phase of STC Stereo Camera channel of the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS).

The Strategy is a revision of the previous defined one ([RD. 1]) which should be considered obsolete.

Reference Document

[RD. 1] BC-SIM-TN-009 STC GM Observation Strategy Optimization

([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/173](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/173))

[RD. 2] BC-SIM-TN-003_-_Reports_and_Note_Layout_and_Flow Version 2,

([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179))

[RD. 3] BC-SIM-GAF-MA-002 rev.8_SIMBIO-SYS FM User Manual, 2017

[RD. 4] SOIM User Manual v6.0

([10.20371/INAF/TechRep/202](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/202))

[RD. 5] Widrow, B., Kollar, I., & Liu, M. C. (1996). Statistical theory of quantization. IEEE Transactions on instrumentation and measurement, 45(2), 353-361.

([10.1109/19.492748](https://doi.org/10.1109/19.492748))

Acronyms

ACK	Acknowledgment
ADC	Analogical Digit Converter
APID	Application Process IDentifier
ASW	Application SoftWare
CM	Color Mode
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DSNU	Dark Signal not Uniformity
FOP	Flight Operation Procedure
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ICO	Instrument Checkout
IT	Integration Time
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
OBCP	On-Board Control Procedure
OB	Optical Bench
OBSW	On Board Software
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PDS	Planetary Data System
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
RT	Repetition Time
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SOIM	Simulator for Operation of Imaging Missions
SSC	Source Sequence Count
SSMM	Solid State Mass Memory
STC	STereo imaging Channel
S/C	Space-Craft
TC	TeleCommand
TEC	Thermo-Electric Cooler
TM	Telemetry
VIHI	Visible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD. 2] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository (<https://openaccess.inaf.it>) and in the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

Document Organization

Section 1 provides a concise overview of the definitions and assumptions related to:

- The STC instrument (the stereoscopic channel of SIMBIO-SYS),
- Its operations during the GM phase and the parameters of its telecommands,
- The MPO satellite's orbit, its evolution, and the definitions of its various phases (i.e., seasons).

While not exhaustive, this overview covers all essential aspects needed to explain the optimization process detailed in this document, aimed at ensuring the performance and objectives of the STC Channel while minimizing Data Volume (DV). For more in-depth information, please refer to the cited references.

Section 2 outlines the optimization strategy for the STC, describing the tools and approaches selected.

Section 3 addresses the constraints associated with the instrument and the orbit, along with the definition of orbit segments.

Section 4 details the main parameters to be commanded during the GM phase, specifically the integration time and the along-track and cross-track dimensions of the acquisition windows. For each parameter, the underlying assumptions and analysis conducted are presented.

Section 5 summarizes the simulation results, including sample commanded orbit timelines and DV evaluations.

1. Definitions and assumptions

Before the end of the second aphelion (28 September 2027), STC aims to complete a 3D global mapping with stereo imaging at a minimum spatial resolution of 58 m/px. The latter half of the nominal mission will focus on filling coverage gaps and conducting multispectral imaging (Color Mode) of selected regions.

The following sections outline the foundational principles guiding instrument design and orbital positioning to optimize the global mapping observation strategy for STC.

1.1. STC Channel

The STC optical design is shown in Fig. 1 reporting a detailed 3D optical scheme of the instrument. The dual stereo optical system consists of a pair of folding mirrors (Ch-1 and Ch-2) which redirects the $\pm 21.375^\circ$ wide stereo aiming beams along a direction much closer to the optical axis of the system.

Fig. 1 STC 3D optical scheme. The optical path is depicted in red. On the right, the projected on-ground FoV for all the filter frames is depicted. The AT and CT directions are nominally aligned with the detector columns and rows corresponding to the yellow and blue arrows drawn on the detector plane.

The latter part of the instrument is a modified Schmidt telescope which converge in a Si-PIN hybrid CMOS detector. Different filters are mounted with little separation on the same detector as shown. These filters allow:

- The Global Mapping of the Mercury surface which will be performed by acquiring one or both PAN filters. All the three windows (PANH, PANL, FilterX) will be acquired with a compression factor of 7.
- The Color Mode of the Targets which will be performed by acquiring with one or more of the remaining 4 colour filters.

In both the cases the filters will be always acquired together the so-called Win-X a 64x128 window on the detector used to monitoring the dark (see Section 8.1.2.2 of [RD. 3]).

1.2.Orbit and SK assumptions

1.2.1. Spice Kernels and Seasons

Current document describes the STC Strategy under the assumption of the Spice Kernel defined by bc_plan_v430_20241016_001 (delivered before 23-10-2024).

It is assumed that STC will operate in the first 3 Aphelion phases with an MTA between 138 and 222. Aphelions phases are so defined:

	APH0	APH1	APH2	APH3	APH4
MTA_START	138.00	138.00	138.00	138.00	138.00
LONG_START	0.1	-179.9	0	179.7	-0.4
DATE	07MAR 16:18:59	03JUN 14:57:00	30AUG 14:36:00	26NOV 14:15:00	22FEB 13:54:00
MTA_STOP	222.00	222.00	222.00	222.00	222.00
LONG_STOP	-179.2	0.7	-179	0.9	-179.3
DATE	05APR 20:49:59	02JUL 20:29:00	28SEP 17:46:00	,25DEC 17:25:00	22MAR 17:03:59
LONG_APH	-1.6	-1.6	-1.6	1.6	-1.6
DATE	22MAR 06:34:29	18JUN 05:43:00	14SEP 04:11:00	11DEC 03:50:00	08MAR 03:28:59

Table 1 Definition of the Aphelion phases for STC channel. Periherm position is reported for the beginning, the center (corresponding to the aphelion), and the end of the Aphelion Season. All column (apart the last one) are referred to 2027.

Following older plane first available orbit for SIMBIO-SYS commissioning was the periherm at 9:38 of 23 April 2025 (corresponding to an MTA of 145.9 and longitude of subnadiral point of -16). Following this plane the first 10 orbits were dedicated to SIMBIO-SYS which decided to dedicate the first 5 to functional tests.

Maintaining the same assumption on the MTA we assume to start the commissioning at the orbit with periherm at 10 March '27 8:00:59 AM with a longitude of the subnadiral point of -16.251 and an MTA of 146.0441.

Same data provided in *Table 1* is described by following figure.

Fig. 2 Figure reports the different STC aphelion season including MTA variation, longitude at boresight at perihelion and Sun Distance.

1.2.2. STC GM Orbits operativity

Assuming that:

- Is preferred to consume the majority of the data volume at the beginning of the mission to address the challenges of the subsequent phases
- The GM will start at the second half of Aph 0 season,
- Aph 1 should be fully utilized,
- Aph 2 should cover the remaining surface

the operational phases for STC are outlined in Table 2. This table provides, for each Mercury year, the first and last operational orbit of the STC GM, defined by its periapsis in UTC and longitude.

Season	START Aphelion [UTC]	Longitude Perihelion [°]	STOP Aphelion [UTC]	Longitude Perihelion [°]	N-orbit involved
Aph0	2027 MAR 22 07:11:01	-89.8	2027 APR 06 20:23:15	175	159
Aph1	2027 JUN 04 09:48:50	175	2027 JUL 03 17:42:37	-4.73	299
Aph2	2027 AUG 31 07:08:11	-4.27	2027 SEP 14 06:33:06	-90.2	143

Table 2 Operative longitudes and time ranges for covering of the entire Mercury surface.

Given the width of the field of view relative to the instrument's footprint between successive orbits, especially in the polar regions, STC will not need to capture images continuously throughout each orbit during the GM phase. As described in Section 4.3.2 and 5.1, part of the orbit can skip panchromatic filter imaging and instead focus on acquiring specific targets with the color filters (CM).

2. THE STC GLOBAL MAPPING Optimization

STC Observation strategy was studied to define the better solution to plan the Global Mapping for STC Stereo Channel optimizing the instrument performance (from an imaging and a photogrammetric point of view) and the allocated resources: i.e. data volume (DV) and number of telecommands TCs available.

Different issues were optimized in the last years to reduce the DV simplifying the strategy and allowing the same performances.

Due to the flexibility of its design, in order to properly operate STC, some PSS (Symbiosys TC Parameter) defined in the Flight Operation Procedure (FOP) planned on-ground must be defined and are reported in *Table 3*:

Description	PSS-ID Involved	Reason
Filters combination	PSS01101- PSS01104 PSS00501- PSS00504	1 or more filter could be acquired
window size in pixels to be acquired for each filter	PSS01101- PSS01104 PSS00501- PSS00504	windows dimensions is limited by APS granularity, vertically dimensions (AT) are fixed , horizontal ones (CT) are defined to guarantee the overlapping between two consecutive orbits
Repetition Time (RT)	PSS01629	To guarantee the overlapping between two consecutive acquisitions on the same orbit
Compression Factor	PSS00601-3	Nominally fixed
Integration Time	PSS01501	Minimum between the smearing and the integration time (for both the channels) needed to achieve the maximum limit of the linearity range

Table 3 Table summarizing the formal parameters (PSS) estimated by the simulations to perform the planning of the STC Global Mapping.

In order to save the DV and simplify the instrument operations and its implementation in the telecommands it is convenient to divide a spacecraft orbit around Mercury in segments. The effect of this simplification is that the number of the segments has an impact on the definition of the Integration time and Repetition time. Which means that a larger number of orbit segments can strongly increase the SNR of the STC data and reduce the DV.

The optimization process will proceed as follows:

- Definition of a SK (Spice Kernels) based dataset;
- Evaluation on the basis of the design parameters of the PSS (Symbiosys TC Parameter) and timeline;
- Simulation to estimate DV.

The optimization process follows the diagram of *Fig. 2* applied to a predefined timeline (i.e. an Aphelion or its subset).

Fig. 3 Optimization process pipeline

The tool developed is based on MATLAB and exploits the Spice Kernels. The tool is extension of the Simulator for Operation of Imaging Missions (SOIM) software ([RD. 4]) which, at the current date is applied to 6 instruments: the three Monitor Cameras (MCAM) on board of BepiColombo Mission, and the three channels of SIMBIO-SYS, all onboard of BepiColombo mission.

The starting point (blue square) is the generation of a dataset for a particular phase of the mission. This dataset is the result of an oversampling of the SK data to a minimal time step (1 second) of:

- the footprints of the channels of the instrument
- the illumination conditions
- the boresight on ground intercept and its velocity

The dataset generation allows to provide all the information derived by SK needed for strategy optimization.

Second phase (green) is the effective optimization of the timeline (orbit segmentation and strategy) and of the PSS to guarantee the input required (in this case we consider as input Number of TC, AT overlapping and CT overlapping).

Once all these parameters are defined for each segment of every orbit of the phase considered (for example one Aphelion), the same TCs are simulated to follow the requirements and the evaluation of the DV.

3. CONSTRAINTS FROM THE INSTRUMENT DESIGN

3.1. Field of view and Channels

STC is composed of two sub-channels (i.e. High (-H) and Low (-L) see *Fig. 1*). The angle between each sub-channel lines of sight and the instrument boresight is nominally 20° and it will be confirmed

during Commissioning phase in the first part of the Aphelion 0 before the beginning of the Science Phase.

The panchromatic filters have a FoV, that will be calibrated, on average of $4.61^\circ \times 2.31^\circ$ corresponding to 768×384 pixels.

The PAN filters will be acquired together for most of the GM phase, excluding the region near poles where one of the channel will be pointed to the planet dark side. In this case only one of the panchromatic filters will be acquired (synchronously with the Win-X).

Both the PAN windows will be acquired with the same dimension:

- Along Track (AT) dimension will be always commanded with the maximum FoV (384 px) (overlapping optimization will be solved by the commanded RT)
- Cross Track (CT) dimension will be limited by 4 possibilities (because of its granularity) guaranteeing a minimum CT dimension equal to the AT one. The windows will be acquired with a step of 128 px corresponding to about 0.4° (see next table).

FoV CT [°]	FoV CT [px]
2.3911	384
3.1878	512
3.9842	640
4.7802	768

Table 4 FoV in cross track direction defined by the two PAN windows of STC during the GM phase.

Fig. 4– Projection on the surface of Mercury, at the perihelion of Aphelion 0, of the footprints (FoVs) of the panchromatic filter of SIMBIO-SYS: STC –PAN H and -L (respectively in blue and red). Simulations: in a) projection on the Mercury sphere and in b) equirectangular projection, of 4 consecutive acquisitions with a repetition time of 10 sec (which does not guarantee the AT overlapping) visualized in the Messenger basemap Color Global Mosaic

3.2.STC Typical orbit

STC operates in GM only during the first Aphelions (between a MTA of 138° and 222°). Mercury in this phase covers a mean of 0.28° of MTA for each BepiColombo orbit. Illumination conditions at Aphelion obliges the instrument to work in this phase around the perihelion. Fig. 4 shows a typical GM orbit divided in operation segments; we assume in this report a number of TCs equal to 20.

Fig. 5 Subdivision in segments for an MPO aphelion orbit. For each segment STC is represented in red, blue, green depending on whether it is working, respectively, with the single forward or backward channel, or both channels.

Considering that each time the MPO will flip around its axis (2 times every mercury year) the channel oriented in the same direction of the S/C velocity will change; thus, we do not refer hereafter to channels as their nominal names (PAN-H or PAN-L) but forward or backward.

This has an obvious impact in the CT overlapping calculation where it must be considered that in the orbit at aphelion, closest to sun, the overlapping must be considered for the channel HIGH with the channel LOW and viceversa.

GM orbit starts with the forward (PAN-H or PAN-L depending on the True Anomaly) channel acquisition between the moment of the intercept of the terminator (near the pole) by the PAN boresight until the other channel boresight reaches the South pole.

The following orbit segment works in GM with both the channels. The last segment covers the time when the forward channel arrives on the line separating the illuminated and the dark hemisphere and when the backward channel achieves the same line. This last segment ends when the dayside is out of the FoV of both the channel.

Document BC-SIM-TN-009
Date 18/11/2024
Issue 1
Revision 0
Page 14 of 34

The orbit segments (excluding the first and last ones) are defined to ensure that the range of subnadir latitudes covered by two consecutive TCs is equal..

Their division is described in detail in the next section.

TC-N	Mode	Fop ID	Fop Names
1	Backward Ch	ASSF301/ ASSF302	STC Science SURF SINGLE PANH /L
2	GM	ASSF307	STC Science SURF NOMINAL GM
.....	GM	ASSF307	STC Science SURF NOMINAL GM
N-1	GM	ASSF307	STC Science SURF NOMINAL GM
Nth	Forward Ch	ASSF302/ ASSF301	STC Science SURF SINGLE PANL/H

Table 5 TCs commanded during a typical orbit of STC (N is defined equal to 20) and the Flight Operation Procedures (FOPs) to be commanded.

Table 5 reports the functional operation procedures associated with the different orbit segments which includes the STC Science Surface acquisition of one of the two channels or the acquisition of both the channels.

From a point of view of the commanding STC will acquire:

- in continuous mode (each TC will stop the previous one and will start a new sequence of acquisitions, see [RD. 3] for details) for all the orbit sectors apart the last one.
- In non-continuous mode (Base on a number of pre-defined acquisitions). It is the case of the last TC (Nth in Table 5).

In manner to avoid the subsequent use of a STOP TC.

Given the width of the field of view relative to the instrument's footprint between successive orbits, especially in the polar regions, **STC will not need to capture images for all the segments. As described in Section 4.3.2 and 5.1, part of the orbit can skip acquiring GM images and not all the TCs reported in Table 5 will be commanded in each orbit.**

In the case of Aphelion, note that the MPO flip, maneuver applied at each Aphelion, obliges the use, during single channel acquisition, only PANL (in the case of first Aphelion) (which represent the forward channel in this phase) before the TA 180 and PANH after TA 180.

In all the Science FOPs reported in Table 5 formal parameters (details in *Table 3*) are:

- The Integration Time,
- The Repetition Time,
- the CT dimension of the windows

3.2.1. Segments Orbit definition

Considering the purpose of the instrument to perform a complete GM in stereo mode we assume, as best solution, the orbit segments as function of the subnadir latitudes defined constant for each aphelion. During an Aphelion season the limits of the subnadir latitude will be fixed and they will change the next aphelion due to the changing argument and distance of the periherm.

As shown in Fig. 5 the segments definition is based on two kinds of event:

- Subnadir latitude in which the dayside is seen by only one PAN
- Subnadir latitude in which dayside is seen by both the PAN

These events are not constant due to the orbit evolution. For this reason, we fix for each aphelion phase two latitude limits:

- The first is the maximum near South pole of the subnadiral latitudes (evaluated for each orbit of the Aphelion) in which both the channels are looking at the dayside.
- The second is the minimum near North pole of the subnadiral latitudes (evaluated for each orbit of the Aphelion) in which both the channels are looking at the dayside.

These correspond respectively to the maximum of the latitudes defined in Fig. 5 as event 20 and the minimum of the latitudes defined as event 2.

Fig. 6 Subdivision in segments for an MPO aphelion orbit. For each segment STC is represented in red, blue, green depending on whether it is working, respectively, with the single forward or backward channel, or both channels. MPO orbit is counterclockwise.

Considering the Aphelion 1 phase, Fig. 6 shows the subnadiral latitude associated with the two events (associated to the first and last GM TCs of Table 5). Both the parameters have a variation less than 0.31° during the Aphelion.

Fig. 7 Definition of the beginning and end of GM following SK for each orbit of Aphelion 1 phase. Dot line represents the minimum value for the GM starting and max value for GM stop.

Considering these assumptions, the timing definition of the TCs reported in Table 2 can be fixed by the following definitions and equations.

TC-N	Description	Definition	Mode
1	Subnadir latitude corresponding to the first occasion in the orbit in which the Forward Ch boresight intersects the terminator.	$L_s(1) : Fw \in Dayside$	Forward
2	Minimum subnadir latitude (for all the Aphelion) corresponding to the first occasion in the orbit in which both channel have passed the terminator.	$L_s(2) = \min(L_s):$ $Both \in Dayside \forall Orbits \in Aph$	GM
i	Uniform division of the subnadir latitudes between $L_s(2)$ and $L_s(20)$.	$L_s(i) = L_s(2) + (i - 2) \frac{L_s(20) - L_s(2)}{18}$	GM
20	Maximum subnadir latitude (for all the Aphelion) $L_s(20)$ corresponding to the last occasion in which both the channels are in the dayside. Acquisitions will continue until Backward Ch boresight intersects a region with incidence angle greater than 90° .	$L_s(20) = \max(L_s):$ $Both \in Dayside \forall Orbits \in Aph$	Backward

Table 6 Definition of the subnadir latitudes which define the orbit segmentation of STC GM. Each segment is defined by a TC. Same TCs are reported in Table 5.

Given the width of the field of view relative to the instrument's footprint between successive orbits, especially in the polar regions, **STC will not need to acquire images for all the segments. As described in Section 4.3.2 and 5.1, part of the orbit can skip acquiring GM images implying that not all the orbit segments reported in Table 6 Table 5 will be used for GM acquisitions.**

4. Parameters Definition

4.1. Integration time

4.1.1. Assumptions

STC does not permit the definition of multiple Integration Times (one for each window); this means that a unique formal parameter is commanded for both channels involved in science global mapping. The nominal IT is, therefore defined as the minimum (between the two STC channels) between the smearing and the IT needed to reach the maximum range of the linearity range. In this way the highest Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) is accomplished avoiding the saturation of the other filter.

SNR is evaluated considering the contribution of the Photon Noise, the Read Out Noise and the Dark Current evaluated during on ground calibration.

Integration times are defined considering the Instrument Transfer Law (ITL) of the instrument and the solar radiance back-reflected by Mercury Surface, obtained using the Hapke Reflectance Model applied to images taken with filters of the MDIS Instrument on board of MESSENGER NASA Mission (considering the Metabei dataset).

Smearing is considered as the time needed by the on ground footprint boresight to move of $\frac{1}{4}$ of the along track (taking in account the high emission angle of STC) pixel dimension.

4.1.2. Analysis

As illustrated in *Fig. 7*, smearing has no impact on the Global Mapping phase due to the short integration times, which are estimated to range from a minimum of 0.1 ms to an average of 1.5 ms.

Fig. 8 In (a) the Integration Times defined to reach the limits of the linearity range for both the filters and the smearing time estimated by SK simulation. In (b) the expected theoretical SNR, the operative one considering 11 Orbit segments and the one considering 21 Orbit Segments.

The integration time can be therefore considered as the minimum Integrator Time for the two channels. The simulations demonstrated a minimum SNR of 193 for aphelion orbits (with a maximum of 245) while a minimum of 200 and a maximum of 229 at the limit of the Aphelion phases where the orbit plane differs from the plane that includes the incident ray and the normal of the surface at the observer point. Considering the quantization linked to the division of the orbit in segments it is clear that the SNR will be, for each orbit segment the minimum of the one expected during the segment. The optimization of the performance is therefore consequent to the number of operative segments available in each orbit.

4.2.AT overlapping and Repetition Time

The availability of a continuous mosaicking of the PAN acquisitions would be important in order to guarantee a stable image block both for the 2D and 3D mapping. **Simulations have demonstrated the requirement of a minimum overlapping of the 15% both in along track and cross track direction.**

4.2.1. Assumptions

Along track overlapping define the numbers of pixels overlapped between one acquisition and the following one. This parameter has a strong impact on the Data Volume but the redundancy of the observations allows to perform Bundle Adjustment between the acquisitions supplying the corrected

orientation of the Instrument Frame. This overlapping will be useful for the alignment of the images obtained in following acquisitions, allowing the identification of a number of tie points in the overlapping area able to accomplish a stable image mosaicking.

4.2.2. Analysis

The RT can be evaluated as function of three parameters:

- the pixel on ground (pog)
- the boresight velocity (v_b)
- the Overlapping required

First two parameters are both dependant on the considered PAN window and on the time.

The $pog(ch, t)$ defines the along track dimension at a time t of the pixel on ground defined near boresight of the channel ch . In the case of STC which has strong emission angle the best approach is to define the two versors of the boresight and of the next row pixels (taking advantage of “getfov” SK procedure) and using “sincpt” SK procedure to obtain the two 3D points seen by the two optical rays. The two versors intercepts are used to defined the PoG.

The velocity $v_b(ch, t)$ of the intercept of the boresight if defined as:

$$v_b(ch, t) = \frac{\delta b}{\delta t}$$

Where b is the boresight intercept (using “sincpt” SK procedure) with the Mercury spheroid.

The Repetition Time to be commanded in each orbit segment can be defined as the minimum repetition time operable in order to reach the minimum overlapping along track required for all the orbit segment considered and for both channels synchronically. The Repetition time can be defined as the minimum of the ratio of pog and v_b parameters multiplied for the minimum overlapping along track in pixel for both channels ($OVER_{perc}$, in this case 15%):

$$RT = OVER_{perc} \min_{ch,t} \left(\frac{pog(ch, t)}{v_b(ch, t)} \right) 0.384$$

Following this definition, it is possible to calculate, for each orbit segment, the repetition time (RT) required to ensure at least a 15% along-track overlap at both the start and end of the segment. *Table 7* shows the lower and upper RT limits for each Aphelion, calculated using this heuristic across individual orbit segments (where 1 represents entry into the dayside at the south pole and 20 corresponds to the north pole).

Orbit Sectors	Aphelion 0		Aphelion 1		Aphelion 2	
	min	max	min	max	min	max
1	18.75	24.42	16.09	22.13	13.96	20.22
2	17.27	20.77	14.83	17.98	12.91	15.10
3	15.56	17.19	13.11	14.68	11.03	12.26
4	13.38	14.63	11.28	12.44	9.39	10.39

5	11.71	12.72	9.81	10.77	8.15	8.97
6	10.36	11.18	8.67	9.48	7.22	7.92
7	9.31	10.01	7.84	8.53	6.58	7.18
8	8.56	9.17	7.27	7.86	6.18	6.71
9	8.06	8.60	6.96	7.48	6.05	6.45
10	7.83	8.25	6.89	7.23	6.05	6.35
11	7.80	8.05	6.90	7.17	6.16	6.35
12	7.83	8.05	7.10	7.24	6.42	6.65
13	8.06	8.28	7.36	7.60	6.84	7.12
14	8.41	8.69	7.81	8.15	7.50	7.87
15	9.01	9.32	8.54	9.01	8.43	8.93
16	9.89	10.26	9.58	10.22	9.67	10.39
17	11.10	11.62	10.95	11.87	11.29	12.33
18	12.70	13.62	12.67	14.24	13.35	15.11
19	12.08	15.95	12.47	16.99	13.30	18.41
20	12.56	16.56	13.32	17.60	14.40	18.92

Table 7 Limits of the RTs in seconds commanded during the different aphelions in the different Orbit Sectors.

Note: considering the old definition of the orbit segments in [RD. 1] we report here the comparison between the assumption of using 10 or 20 number of segments: Fig. 8 shows the results of this estimation in the case of the first and last orbit of aphelion 1 and Aphelion 2 (the two Aphelion dedicated to GM) both in the case we assume a number of TC (and relative number of orbit segments) of 11 or 21.

Fig. 9 Evaluation of the RT associated to the STC TCs as a function of the RT for the first (continue) and last (segmented) orbit of the Aphelion 1 and Aphelion 2. In warmer colors (red and yellow) the evaluation for 11 TCs and in colder colors (green and blue) 21 TCs.

The plot underlies the decrease of the RT during the Aphelion 1 between the first (continuous) and the last (dotted) orbit.

For the lower latitudes, the use of an high number of TCs (i.e. 21 instead of the previous considered 11) increases the RT of the 16% with the relative impact on the DV.

Considering that the RT is defined as the minimum time to guarantee the overlapping for both the channels for a defined orbit segment, the number of TCs and the orbit segmentation have a strong impact on this parameter.

4.3. CT overlapping and CT dimension

4.3.1. Assumptions

Considering the across track configuration, in order to guarantee a sufficient number of interesting points in the overlapping areas of images to be mosaicked, even in this case we assume the same limit of 15% between two consecutive orbits for each latitude.

This overlapping should be guaranteed for each latitude of the same acquisition.

As described in Section 3.1 algorithmic and physical constraints impose that the number of pixels both along and cross track be a multiple of 64 and that the minimum window CT size allowed be 384 pixels.

Considering a symmetrical acquisition CT this granularity of the detector acquisitions CT brings to an overconsumption (in terms of pixel) which can be considered as a quantization noise [RD. 5] with a mean of 64 pixel for each acquisition and a standard deviation equal to $128/\sqrt{12}$.

4.3.2. Analysis

CT dimension is evaluated as the maximum between the two channels on the orbit sector (OS), following the equation:

$$CTdim^* = \left(\left(\frac{\alpha_{r_orbit}}{(100 - over_{PERC})} \frac{100}{\Delta Long} \right) \right)$$

Where

α_{r_orbit} is the planet rotation (during a MPO orbit)

$\Delta Long$ is the Cross Track coverage defined by Spice Kernels.

$over_{PERC}$ is the overlapping cross track in pixels (nominally 15% for the Global Mapping)

Note that $CTdim$ must be rounded up considering that it must be a multiple of 128 assuming symmetrical acquisitions and greater or equal the AT dimension (384 px).

It is clear that for the polar regions the required overlapping could be reached with simple acquisitions with this minimal window dimension thanks to the singularity of the pole respect the polar BepiColombo orbit. The use of minimal acquisition windows is, nevertheless, more problematic from a stability of the mosaicking of the GM. The large FoV of STC, furthermore, allows,

in these regions, to guarantee the planet coverage operating alternative orbits. In this manner the overlapping should be guaranteed not with the subsequent orbits but with the following ones. This strategy has three effects:

- The reduction of the DV avoiding overlapping for each orbit
- The use of greater CT swath reduces the number of images
- It improves the angular information needed for the mosaicking process and for the bundle adjustment procedures between subsequent acquisitions and between orbits.

As shown in *Fig. 9* the cross track overlapping should be guaranteed, near polar regions, even without working 3 orbits every 4.

Fig. 10 - Percentage of superposition with respect to the boresight latitude of the FoV of one orbit with the consecutive one (red line) and with the following three (blue and green and magenta lines), at the beginning of the mission (Aphelion 1).

Using the full CT FoV at Aphelion 1 results in an overlap of more than 400 pixels at periherm and over 700 pixels near the polar regions. For this reason, we propose that STC operates near the poles, skipping up to four orbits and allowing GM to utilize between 16 and 20 TCs per orbit.

Lat [°]	Each orbit [%]	Avoiding 1 orbit [%]	Avoiding 2 orbit [%]	Avoiding 3 orbit [%]
-80	95	88	82	77
-70	89	76	63	51
-60	83	61	41	22

-50	76	45	17	0
-40	69	28	0	0
-30	62	11	0	0
-20	56	0	0	0
-10	52	0	0	0
0	49	0	0	0
10	49	0	0	0
20	52	0	0	0
30	57	0	0	0
40	65	18	0	0
50	73	36	5	0
60	81	55	34	11
70	87	71	57	41
80	95	90	82	75

Table 8: Summary of the data presented in Fig. 9 percentage of CT overlap at full FoV between one orbit and the immediately following orbit, or skipping 1, 2, or 3 orbits. Results pertain to Aphelion 1.

Fig. 10 illustrates the system developed to manage GM operations by adjusting orbit segments and CT size. In the diagram, orbits are shown in blue, with a transparent overlay representing the changing footprint pattern across latitudes.

Near the equator, where the CT is smaller, STC operates in every orbit. As latitude increases, STC operates every other orbit, with an expanded CT. At the highest latitudes, STC may skip up to three consecutive orbits. The red markers indicate orbits where STC operates in GM mode.

Fig. 11 The figure shows a cycle of five GM orbits near the north pole. The regions where the instrument is active are highlighted in red, indicating data acquisition from bottom to top. Initially, data is collected in every orbit, then in alternating orbits (green), skipping two orbits (yellow), and finally in every fourth orbit (blue). The cross-track dimension of acquisitions increases to ensure cross-track overlap.

This strategy reserves specific time windows during which STC should remain inactive, allowing the channel to be used for CM acquisitions that benefit from strong overlap. STC will acquire data using a limited set of BB filters in one orbit, then in the next orbit, it will cover much of the same region with the remaining BB filters. This approach optimizes the SNR of acquisitions by adjusting the integration time for each filter. As shown in *Table 8*, the overlap between two consecutive orbits can reach over 80% at latitudes above 60°.

The following image shows the same diagram, with red highlighting the orbital sections where STC operates in GM mode. The green sections represent orbits where, since GM is inactive and two consecutive orbits are skipped, STC can operate in CM mode. In these cases, two filters are used in one orbit and the remaining two in the following orbit.

Fig. 12 Diagram of CM target integration within GM operations. This figure builds on Figure 10, highlighting in red the orbital sections where STC operates in GM mode. The green sections indicate two segments across consecutive orbits where STC is free to acquire CM targets.

Notes: As in the case of the Along Track dimensions, even for CT one simulation have demonstrated a strong impact of the number of the segments assumed and the DV consumption.

As example Fig. 12 shows the case of the first orbit of Aphelion 1 analyzed considering 10 (dotted lines) or 20 (continuous lines) orbit segments and considering the use of consecutive (red) or alternate (green) orbits. The figure shows how it should be assumed to work every orbit in the first and last segments of the orbit corresponding to South and Nord poles (subnadirial latitude less than -30S or greater than 45N).

Fig. 13 Optimized CT dimension of the PAN acquisition in the case of consecutive orbits (red) or alternate ones (green). Dotted line shows the optimization in case of an amount of 20 orbit section. Red regions represent the comparison between the 10 TCs planning and the 20 TCs planning. They underly the segments in which there is a strong increase in RT for the 10 TCs case which means they represent the gain in the choice of a greater number of TCs.

Fig. 12 underlines in green the gain obtained assuming 21 TCs. As for the RT, even in this case, an increased number of orbit sections will provide an optimized strategy.

5. Results

5.1. Parameters Overview

This process can be extended to all the orbits (which share the same segments definition). It is possible for each segment of the orbit to define the minimum CT dimension to guarantee the right overlapping with consecutive orbit varying the number of orbits to jump near poles.

The result of this analysis is shown in next figures (*Fig. 13, Fig. 14, Fig. 15*) which show for each aphelion four parameters which describes the operative mode following the definition of next table.

The commanded dimension	dimension in pixel of both the PAN filters acquired
Percentile Overlapping	percentile of pixel overlapped with the subsequent acquisition at the same latitude
Pixels overlapping	number of pixels overlapped with the subsequent acquisition at the same latitude
Avoiding orbits	Number of orbits in which the instrument will not work after the one considered

All the diagrams illustrate the evolution of these parameters across the three aphelions. Each diagram represents the orbit number (relative to the start of the aphelion operational phase, as defined in Table 2) on the x-axis and the orbit segment number on the y-axis.

Each page provides an example of the commands for the first orbit associated with the aphelion season considered, defining the following parameters for the 20 telecommands:

- **Time (UTC):** Time of the command execution
- **N-TC [#]:** Telecommand number and orbit segment
- **SbNad Lat [°]:** Latitude of the sub-nadir point at the specified time
- **Ch-H/L [°]:** Latitude of the boresight intersection on the planet for the two channels
- **TC:** Telecommand required
- **RT [s]:** Repetition time in seconds
- **Avoiding Orbits:** Number of subsequent orbits that can be skipped for this orbit sector
- **CT Dim [px]:** Cross-track dimension in pixels

The 21st row of each table indicates the end of the last segment that does not require a telecommand.

Fig. 14 Simulation of the CT parameters of the GM for the Apelion 0 phase.

Time UTC	N-TC [#]	SbNad Lat [°]	Ch L [°]	Ch H [°]	TC	RT [s]	Avoiding Orbits	CT Dim [px]
6:36:09	1	-78.9	-89.7	NaN	STC-L	24.2	3	384
6:44:28	2	-80.9	-71.7	-89.4	GM	20.8	3	640
6:48:07	3	-71.4	-63	-79.7	GM	17.2	2	640
6:51:36	4	-61.8	-54.2	-69.3	GM	14.6	1	640
6:54:54	5	-52.2	-45.3	-59	GM	12.7	1	768
6:58:05	6	-42.6	-36.4	-48.9	GM	11.2	0	512
7:01:08	7	-33.1	-27.4	-38.7	GM	10	0	512
7:04:05	8	-23.5	-18.3	-28.7	GM	9.17	0	640
7:06:57	9	-13.9	-9	-18.8	GM	8.6	0	640
7:09:46	10	-4.34	0.298	-8.96	GM	8.25	0	640
7:12:32	11	5.24	9.71	0.746	GM	8.05	0	640
7:15:17	12	14.8	19.2	10.4	GM	8.04	0	640
7:18:02	13	24.4	28.9	19.9	GM	8.12	0	512
7:20:48	14	34	38.6	29.3	GM	8.44	0	512
7:23:37	15	43.5	48.5	38.7	GM	9.05	1	768
7:26:30	16	53.1	58.4	47.8	GM	9.96	1	640
7:29:27	17	62.7	68.4	56.9	GM	11.3	2	768
7:32:32	18	72.3	78.6	66	GM	13.3	3	640
7:35:42	19	81.8	88.7	74.9	GM	15.9	3	384
7:36:06	20	83	76	89.5	STC-H	16.5	3	384
7:41:29	-	81.8	NaN	89.7	STOP			

Table 9 Timeline of the TCs for the first orbit of Apelion Season 0 (2027 MAR 22)

Document	BC-SIM-TN-009
Date	18/11/2024
Issue	1
Revision	0
Page	32 of 34

Next page (see Fig. 16) shows the merging of the diagrams in the three aphelions. CT dimensions reach the minimum value (384) near poles where the instrument is operative 1 orbit every four. This allows to minimize DV consumption and maintain the percentage overlapping over the 15% with a maximum of 36% in the same regions.

Fig. 17 Simulation of the CT parameters of the GM for all the three Aphelions. Orbit number should be consider as cumulative.

5.2.DV production

The RT and CT dimensions defined and reported in previous sections, and the Compression Ratio assumed to be fixed to 7 (bit rate 2 bit/pix) are the parameters to be used for the DV estimate during the GM. The data rate evaluation allows us to report the DV estimate for the main Aphelion's of the BepiColombo missions.

It is clear that the margin to optimize this consumption and improve the performance of the instrument, radiometrically and geometrical, is the possibility to increase the number of orbit segmentation as possible. We define number of segments equal to 20 (corresponding to 20 TCs) in manner to have a gain in the DV around the 7% with respect to the previous considered case of 10 orbit segments (see [RD. 1]). DV consumption considering the CT dimensions, RT and strategy described is reported in *Table 12*.

Aphelion	Operative Orbits [#]	DV [Gb]	Mean DV for orbit [Mb]
0	155	33.6	216.6
1	295	74.6	249.4
2	139	42.0	293.8
Total		150.2	

Table 12 DV consumption for the GM of STC during Aphelion seasons following the operative time windows defined in Table 2.

Previous simulations, considering a number of orbit sector equal to 10 and a limited use of the overlapping (less than 10%) have demonstrated a consumption of STC channel with a consumption of 161.75 Gb.